

FUNCTIONAL RESPONSE OF LADY BIRD BEETLE *Cheilomenes sexmaculata* (coleoptera: coccinellidae) LARVAE TO OKRA APHID *APHIS GOSSYPYII* OF OKRA IN LABORATORY CONDITION

S.G. Lonagre*, A.V.Kolhe, And D. B. Undirwade

Ph.D. Scholar Department of Agricultural Entomology,
Associate Director Research ZARS Sindewahi Dist ChandrapurHead Department of Agricultural Entomology,
Dr. Panjabrao Deshmukh Krishi Vidyapeeth, Akola 444104 Maharashtra, India.swatilonagre13@gmail.com

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Abstract

A functional response study of the predator *Cheilomenes sexmaculata* larvae to various densities of okra aphid *Aphis gossypii* was conducted under laboratory condition of 25 ± 10 C, 60 ± 5 % RH and 16L: 8D photoperiod based on Holling's disk equation. *Cheilomenes sexmaculata* shows type II functional response to increasing densities of prey i.e. *Aphis gossypii* at cumulative exposure of 12 and 24 hours to its prey. The attack rate or searching efficiency for *C. sexmaculata* against *Aphis gossypii* was found to be higher at 12 hrs (0.08) than at 24 hrs (0.06) of exposure as against it at 12 hrs handling time was found to be shorter (0.03) than 24 hrs (0.05) respectively.

Key words: Functional response, *Cheilomenes sexmaculata*, *Aphis gossypii* Photoperiod, Attack rate, Searching efficacy, Holling's disk equation.

Introduction

Predation is assumed to be one of the significant biotic mortality factors reducing insect pest populations, and their use in insect pest management programs has received increased attention because of the current need to reduce the exclusive use of insecticides for pest control (Atlihan et al., 2010). The functional response of a predator is a key factor regulating the population dynamics of predator-prey systems. It describes the rate at which a predator kills its prey at different prey densities and can thus determine the efficiency of a predator in regulating prey populations (Murdoch and Oaten, 1975).

Depending on the density of prey the predatory response are vary and that can be measures in terms of number and also the prey eaten according to their density called numerical and functional responses. Functional response is defined as the relationship between the number of prey consumed per predator and the prey density (Solomon 1949) and is a valuable tool for assessing the potential impact of a natural enemy on pest population growth and predicting the potential for success of biological control agents (Tully et al. 2005). Holling (1959) categorized functional responses into three basic types. The type I response is characterized by a linear rise with a constant attack rate over all prey densities until satiation is reached. In the type II response, the attack rate decreases as prey density increases. Type III is represented by a sigmoid curve where the attack rate increases with increasing prey density and decreases toward satiation. Most studies are confined to type II and III responses because these are the most commonly observed in nature (Juliano 2001).

Ladybird beetles (Coccinellidae: Coleoptera) are important predators in natural and agricultural habitats and prey upon many economically important pests, including aphids, mealybugs, scale insects, thrips, leaf hoppers, mites and other soft bodied insects (Dixon, 2000). Biological control is an effective means of controlling insect pests in the field of agriculture by the use of natural enemies because it is an environmentally sound and effective means of mitigating pest density. Recently, there has been increasing interest of growers to utilize this beneficial predator as an alternative to insecticides to manage insect pests of field and horticultural crops in IPM programs. The predation is assumed to be one of the significant biotic mortality factor reducing insect pest populations, and their use in insect pest management programs has received increased attention due to the current need to reduce the exclusive use of insecticides for pest control. Due to growing economic and environmental concerns involved in the use of synthetic chemicals there is a dire need to develop an alternate measure for the sustainable management of small, soft-bodied, sap sucking insects that cause severe damage to various field crops, fruits and vegetables

Different bio-control agents are available for the management of insect pests.

Material and Methods

Functional response of the predator larvae of *Cheilomenes sexmaculata* to the okra was studied under laboratory conditions. The culture of predator and host was collected from the okra as and when required from the experimental field. Study was conducted at constant temperature of 25 ± 10 c with 16L: 8D photoperiod in incubator with 60 ± 5 % RH maintained using saturated salt solution of $MgNO_3$. Predators as above was collected from host crop and starved for 24hrs at $25^{\circ}C$ in the incubator in order to standardize their appropriate appetite and their weighed by using microbalance to record initial fresh body weights prior to being introduced individually into 9 to 12 cm diameter petridishes together with 5, 10,20,40,80,120,240 and 360 various aphid densities on excised okra leaves stuck to agar medium. Medium size aphids were selected. One of every two petridishes was placed in large transparent box with saturated salt solution with $MgNO_3$ in small cup. Larvae of *Cheilomenes sexmaculata* were randomly assigned to various aphid density treatments as above. At each aphid density 5 to 8 replicates was used. At aphid densities of 360 for *Cheilomenes sexmaculata* larvae was weighed using a micro-balance (accurate to 0.001 mg) to record their initial fresh body weights prior to being introduced into the feeding arenas. Thereafter, the petridishes was checked every 3 hrs after releasing the predator into the petri dishes for up to 24 hrs and the number of aphids consumed was noted, but the aphids consumed was not replace during the feeding time.

To determine the shape, a polynomial regression was fitted to observe proportions of prey killed against N, and the shape of this polynomial fit was determined. If the proportion killed initially increases with the number of prey, this is sufficient to identify a type III functional response. If, on the other hand, the proportion killed declines monotonically with the number of prey, this was sufficient to identify a type III functional response. Thus, logistic regressions of proportion of aphids consume against number of aphids offered was used in this way to determine the general shapes of the functional responses of the test predators.

The most widely used description of a type III functional response of invertebrates predator to changes in prey density is the disc equation by Hollings (1959):

$$N_e = AT N_o \div (1+a TH) \dots \dots \dots (1)$$

Where, 'Ne' is the number of prey attacked, 'No; is initial prey density, a is the predator's rate of successful search, 'Th' is the handling time per prey and 'T' is the length of time the predator and prey are exposed to one another. Another deterministic model of a type II functional response, having similar restrictive assumptions but allowing for

exploitation, was developed concurrently by Royama (1971) and Rogers (1972). The model known as the "random predator" equation:

$$N_e = N_0 \{1 - \exp [a (T_h N_e - T)]\} \dots \dots (2)$$

Where, 'Ne' is the number of prey attacked, 'No'; is initial prey density, a is the predator's rate of successful search, 'Th' is the handling time per prey and 'T' is the length of time the predator and prey are exposed to one another. For type III functional responses, the precise form of the model incorporating depletion depends on whether the attack constant (a) is a function of initial density (No) or current density (N) (Hassell et al., 1977; Hassell, 1978). The simplest form arises when attack rate (a) is a function of initial density, as in Equation2:

$$N_e = N_0 \{1 - \exp [(d + bN_0) (T_h N_e - T) / (1 + cN_0)]\} \dots (3)$$

Once the type of functional response was determined, the number of aphids killed as a function of aphid density against temperature was plotted, and an iterative nonlinear least-squares regression (SAS Institute, 1985) was used to fit the disc equation and random predator equation to the means and to estimate the parameters for type II functional responses. However, a non-linear least square regression was used to fit Hassell's equation (Equation 3) to the data for type III functional responses.

Results and Discussion

Predatory potential of grub of *Cheilomenes sexmaculata* at varying densities of aphids was assessed in the form of functional response. Hence, on the basis of data that corresponds to the Holling disc equation. The functional response curve obtained is belonging to Holling type II.

The mean aphid consumption of *Cheilomenes sexmaculata* was recorded at varying aphid densities for different time intervals of 3, 6, 9, 12, 15, 18, 21 and 24 hours after exposure and presented in Table 1.

The aphid consumption gradually increased at corresponding aphid densities of 5, 10, 20, 40, 80, 120, 240, 360 ranging from 1.9 to 4.8, 3.1 to 9.4, 5.0 to 17.3, 7.5 to 30.9, 11.5 to 49.0, 16.7 to 69.5, 28.1 to 117.3, 38.6 to 168.6 *Cheilomenes sexmaculata* respectively when recorded at 3 to 24 hrs after exposure. The no. of aphid consumed approaches to the asymptote hyperbolically as aphid density increases (Figure.1). This corresponds to an asymptotically declining proportion of aphid killed (Figure.2). The highest percentage of consumption i.e. 90% and 96% was recorded aphid density of 5 at 12 and 24 hrs then curve goes down with increasing aphid density.

The functional response was further confirmed by estimating logistic regression model. Parameter estimate for logistic regressions of proportion of aphid killed (N_e/N_0) against number of aphid offered for grub of *C. sexmaculata* for 3 to 24 hours are presented in Table 2. The logistic regression for the grub of *C. sexmaculata* had significant linear parameters $P_1 < 0$ (-0.0115, -0.0138, -0.0148, -0.0172, -0.0188, -0.0191, -0.0190, -0.0197). The negative value of the linear parameter ($P_1 < 0$) indicated type II response of ladybird beetle. The type II response is also confirmed as the proportion of aphid consumed by the grub of *C. sexmaculata* declined with increasing aphid density.

The handling time (T_h) and attack rate (a) are the parameters that reflect the significance of functional response as the polynomial logistic regression model suggested Type II functional response for *C. sexmaculata*. The data on predation rate was fitted to the random predator equation to attack rate (a) and handling time (T_h).

The coefficient of attack rate (a) and handling time (T_h) (estimated by Roger's random predator equation) of adults of *C. sexmaculata* is presented in Table 3. Showing handling time and attack rate of 0.03, 0.03, 0.03, 0.04, 0.04, 0.04, 0.05, 0.05 and 0.11, 0.09, 0.09, 0.08, 0.08, 0.07, 0.07, 0.07 respectively.

The attack rate for *C. sexmaculata* against *Aphis gossypii* was found to be higher at 12hrs (0.08hr) than at 24 hrs (0.07hr) of exposure of aphids offered as against it at 12 hrs handling time was found to be shorter

(0.03 hr) than 24 hrs (0.05 hr) of exposure. The maximum predation rate (T/T_h) was found to be 455.40 at 24 hours of exposure period.

The value of coefficient of determination for 3 to 24hr (R^2) = 0.99 and standard error of the estimated parameter indicated that Roger's random predator equation adequately described the functional response of *C. sexmaculata*.

The number of prey consumed increases, the percentage of consumption decreases towards higher prey density which confirms type II response of prey predator relationship confirmed through study conducted on *C. sexmaculata* over their prey i.e. aphids. The highest prey consumption potential of *C. sexmaculata* (168.6 aphid was recorded at 24 hrs of prey offered. Similarly, the highest consumption rate of *C. sexmaculata* for aphid 455.40% was recorded at 24 hrs of prey offered. Highest predation efficiency of each *C. sexmaculata* was recorded at prey density of 5 aphids. The attack rate or searching efficiency for *C. sexmaculata* against *Aphis gossypii* was found to be higher at 12 hrs (0.08) than at 24 hrs (0.06) of exposure as against it at 12 hrs handling time was found to be shorter (0.03) than 24 hrs (0.05) respectively.

Trexler et al., (1988) reported that Type II functional response are evidenced by an initial decreases in the proportion of prey eaten with increasing prey offered. Although three types of functional response described by Holling may occur in coccinellids, the fact is that type II is the most common in these insects, as reported for several ladybird beetles preying on distinct leafhoppers species. Such as *C. septumpunctata* feeding on mustard leafhoppers (Omkar and Shefali srivastava, 2003) *Propylea dissecta* feeding on *Aphis gossypii* (Omkar and Parvez, 2004). *Anegleis cardoni* to varying densities of *Aphis gossypii* (Omkar and Kumar, 2013). The handling time T_h is a good indication of predation rate. According to Nordlund and Morison (1990), the handling time affects the type of functional response, suggesting that the shorter the handling time the faster the curve reaches asymptote. In the present study the handling time T_h for ladybird beetle against aphids was 0.03 hrs after 12 hrs which increased to 0.05 hrs in the cumulative observation taken after 24 hrs of exposure of predator to the prey species. Low handling time reveals the predator to be a good bio control agent. Handling time is proportional to the size of the prey.

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Figure 1: Mean aphid consumption by grub of *C. sexmaculata* on different densities of *Aphis gossypii* after 24 hours of exposure (pooled 2015 and 2016)

Figure 2: Proportion of aphid consumption by grub of *C. sexmaculata* on different densities of *Aphis gossypii* after 24 hours of exposure (pooled 2015 and 2016)

Table 1: Mean prey consumption of grub of *C. sexmaculata* on different prey densities of *Aphis gossypii* after 3, 6,9,12,15,18,21 and 24 hours of exposure (pooled 2015 and 2016)

Sr. no.	N ₀	N _e	P N _e	N _e	P N _e	N _e	P N _e	N _e	P N _e
		3hr		6hr		9hr		12hr	
1	5	1.9 (1.38)h	0.38	3.1 (1.76)g	0.62	3.9 (1.97)h	0.78	4.5 (2.12)h	0.9
2	10	3.1 (1.76)g	0.31	5.2 (2.28)g	0.52	6.9 (2.63)g	0.69	8.0 (2.83)g	0.8
3	20	5.0 (2.24)f	0.25	9.0 (3.00)f	0.45	11.1 (3.33)f	0.56	13.0 (3.60)f	0.65
4	40	7.5 (2.74)e	0.19	14.0 (3.74)e	0.35	18.9 (4.34)e	0.47	20.4 (4.51)e	0.51
5	80	11.5 (3.39)d	0.14	23.5 (4.85)d	0.29	29.4 (5.42)d	0.38	34.6 (5.88)d	0.43
6	120	16.7 (4.09)c	0.13	33.8 (5.81)c	0.28	43.3 (6.58)c	0.36	48.7 (6.98)c	0.41
7	240	28.1 (5.30)b	0.11	52.9 (7.27)b	0.22	67.9 (8.24)b	0.28	80.6 (8.98)b	0.33
8	360	38.6 (6.21)a	0.1	74.8 (8.65)a	0.2	97.4 (9.87)a	0.27	108.6 (10.42)a	0.3
	SE(m±)	1.71		5.31		0.16		0.12	
	C.D (P=0.05)	0.15		0.17		0.52		0.45	
	C.V. at 5%	6.83		8.72		7.59		6.21	

Values in parenthesis are square root transformation values, Prey density (N₀), Prey consumed (N_e), Proportion of prey consumed (P N_e)

Cont...

Sr. no.	N ₀	N _e	P N _e	N _e	P N _e	N _e	P N _e	N _e	P N _e
		15hr		18hr		21hr		24hr	
1	5	4.6 (2.14)h	0.92	4.7 (2.16)h	0.94	4.8 (2.19)h	0.96	4.8 (2.19)h	0.96
2	10	8.9 (2.98)g	0.89	9.1 (3.01)g	0.91	9.3 (3.05)g	0.93	9.4 (3.06)g	0.94
3	20	14.6 (3.82)f	0.73	15.8 (3.97)f	0.79	16.4 (4.04)f	0.82	17.3 (4.16)f	0.86
4	40	24.4 (4.94)e	0.61	26.9 (5.19)e	0.67	28.9 (5.38)e	0.72	30.9 (5.56)e	0.77
5	80	38.7 (6.22)d	0.48	42.6 (6.53)d	0.53	46.1 (6.79)d	0.58	49.0 (7.00)d	0.61
6	120	54.6 (7.39)c	0.45	60.3 (7.76)c	0.5	61.5 (7.84)c	0.51	69.5 (8.34)c	0.58
7	240	91.8 (9.58)b	0.38	101.5 (10.07)b	0.42	110.0 (10.49)b	0.46	117.3 (10.83)b	0.49
8	360	132 (11.49)a	0.36	148.1 (12.17)a	0.41	158.3 (12.58)a	0.43	168.6 (12.98)a	0.46
	SE(m±)	0.14		0.14		0.14		0.16	
	C.D (P=0.05)	0.48		0.49		0.48		0.51	
	C.V. at 5%	6.17		5.98		5.71		5.95	

Values in parenthesis are square root transformation values, Prey density (N₀), Prey consumed (N_e), Proportion of prey consumed (P N_e)

Table 2: Maximum likelihood estimate from logistic regression of proportion of prey (*Aphis gossypii*) eaten as a function of initial prey density by grub of *C. sexmaculata* (n=8) at T=3, 6,9,12,15,18,21 and 24 hours by CATMOD procedure

Parameter	Estimate	SE	X ²	P	Estimate	SE	X ²	P	Estimate	SE	X ²	P
	3hr				6hr				9hr			
Intercept (P₀)	-0.69	0.30	5.19	0.02	0.07	0.27	0.06	0.80	0.56	0.27	4.21	0.04
Linear (P₁)	-0.01	0.007	2.67	0.10	-0.014	0.006	4.94	0.03	-0.01	0.006	6.08	0.014

Quadratic (P₂)	0.00003	0.00004	0.61	0.43	0.00003	0.00003	1.17	0.28	0.00004	0.00003	1.42	0.23
Cubic (P₃)	-2.2E-8	6.969E-8	0.10	0.75	-2.25E-8	5.997E-8	0.14	0.71	-2.16E-8	5.696E-8	0.14	0.70

Parameter	Estimate	SE	X ²	P	Estimate	SE	X ²	P	Estimate	SE	X ²	P
	12hr				15hr				18hr			
Intercept (P₀)	0.99	0.28	12.27	0.0005	1.33	0.30	19.88	<.0001	1.59	0.32	25.32	<.0001
Linear (P₁)	-0.02	0.006	7.92	0.005	-0.02	0.006	8.95	0.003	-0.02	0.006	8.50	0.004
Quadratic (P₂)	0.00005	0.00003	2.05	0.15	0.00006	0.00004	2.51	0.11	0.00005	0.00004	2.23	0.13
Cubic (P₃)	-2.95E-8	5.661E-8	0.27	0.60	-3.67E-8	5.728E-8	0.41	0.52	-3.21E-8	5.846E-8	0.30	0.58

Parameter	Estimate	SE	X ²	P	Estimate	SE	X ²	P
	21hr				24hr			
Intercept (P₀)	1.81	0.33	29.28	<.0001	2.03	0.35	32.87	<.0001
Linear (P₁)	-0.02	0.007	7.77	0.005	-0.02	0.007	7.57	0.006
Quadratic (P₂)	0.00005	0.00004	1.86	0.17	0.00005	0.00004	1.75	0.18
Cubic (P₃)	-2.57E-8	6.005E-8	0.18	0.67	-2.42E-8	6.212E-8	0.15	0.70

If P₁= 0 then TYPE I, If P₁= negative then TYPE II, If P₁= positive then TYPE III

Table 3: Functional response parameter estimate values of attack (a) and handling time (T_h) at 95% confidence limit (CL) for grub of *C. sexmaculata* fed on *Aphis gossypii* at T=3,6,9,12,15,18,21,24 hour obtained by least square method

Model	Parameter	Estimate	SE	3hr			T/T _h	Estimate	SE	6hr		T/T _h	
				95% CL		Lower				Upper	Lower		Upper
				Lower	Upper								
Roger's random predator equation	A	0.11	0.01	0.09	0.14	91.46	0.09	0.01	0.07	0.12	185.18		
	T _h (hrs)	0.03	0.01	0.01	0.05		0.03	0.01	0.008	0.06			

Model	Parameter	Estimate	SE	9hr			T/T _h	Estimate	SE	12hr		T/T _h	
				95% CL		Lower				Upper	Lower		Upper
				Lower	Upper								
Roger's random predator equation	A	0.09	0.01	0.06	0.11	260.86	0.08	0.01	0.06	0.11	320		
	T _h (hrs)	0.03	0.01	0.007	0.06		0.04	0.01	0.006	0.07			

Model	Parameter	Estimate	SE	15hr			T/T _h	Estimate	SE	18hr		T/T _h	
				95% CL		Lower				Upper	Lower		Upper
				Lower	Upper								
Roger's random predator equation	A	0.08	0.01	0.05	0.10	365.85	0.07	0.01	0.05	0.09	401.78		
	T _h (hrs)	0.04	0.01	0.008	0.07		0.04	0.01	0.01	0.08			

Model	Parameter	Estimate	SE	21hr			T/T _h	Estimate	SE	24hr		T/T _h	
				95% CL		Lower				Upper	Lower		Upper
				Lower	Upper								
Roger's random predator equation	A	0.07	0.01	0.05	0.09	426.82	0.07	0.01	0.05	0.09	455.40		
	T _h (hrs)	0.05	0.02	0.01	0.08		0.05	0.01	0.02	0.09			

(a)- Coefficient of attack rate, (Th) – handling time , (T/Th)- Maximum predation rate